

Research

Effects of Blended Instructional Strategy on the Learning Outcome of Adults Undertaking Professional Accounting Programmes in Southwest Nigeria

OLANIPEKUN Olubunmi Adebola

Department of Adult Education and Community Development, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State

***Corresponding author**

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Abstract: *This study investigated the effect of blended instructional strategy on the learning outcome of adults undertaking professional accounting programme in Southwest, Nigeria. The study examined the homogeneity of the experimental and control groups before treatment; and the learning outcome of the experimental and control groups after treatment. The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test two group design (one experimental group and one control group). The population targeted for this study consisted of all adults undertaking professional accounting programme in 9 centres in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample consisted of 41 adults undertaking accounting professional programme (intact class size), drawn from two study centres in Southwest, Nigeria, through a multistage sampling procedure. Performance Test in Basic Accounting (PTBA) and Attitudinal Learning Scale (ALS) were used to collect data. The data collected were subjected to t-test and Analysis of Covariance at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The findings revealed that the use of Blended Learning and Conventional strategy enhanced the performance of adults undertaking accounting professional programme while Blended Learning is the more effective. From the findings derived from this study, it was recommended among others that the use of a Blended Learning strategy should be encouraged in accounting professional programme learning centres so as to enhance better performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme.*

Keywords: *Blended Instructional Strategy, Learning Outcome, Adults, Professional Accounting Programme*

Introduction

Various categories of Adults enrol for professional accounting programmes such as; The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), The Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA), The American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) among others. These

programmes are usually run by accredited or designated training centres. To some extent, the learning outcome of the students is dependent on the instructional strategy used by the tutor or instructor. A good tutor should, therefore, aspire to use innovative instructional strategies.

The conventional strategy of teaching often used by tutors includes the lecture method, expository method, demonstration, and direct instruction, among others. The conventional methods of teaching are observed to dwell more on the transmission of knowledge in a manner that emphasizes memorization. This has been characterized by some educators (Kirshner, Sweller and Clark, 2006; Chandra and Watters, 2012, Audu, 2018) to be an unsatisfactory method of teaching students, especially adults. It involves the unidirectional flow of information from the tutor to the students. It does not encourage process skill acquisition needed for proper understanding of principles, concepts, and facts as the students pay attention while the instructor does all the talking.

The quest to curtail the shortcomings of the conventional methods used in teaching and learning processes culminated in the discovery and suggestions by some researchers (Opara, 2011; Omotayo, Adedayo & Ayeni, 2014), make use of innovative teaching methods such as inquiry method, blended learning, concept mappings, simulations and games, spaced-learning, constructivism, problem-based learning among others. However, the researcher is interested in examining the effect of Blended Learning on learning outcomes of adults undertaking professional accounting programme in Southwest, Nigeria. The learning outcome was measured via performance and attitude towards learning.

It appears that online learning is at least as effective, and often times more effective than traditional, face-to-face classes. This "blended learning" approach combines the best andragogical practices of online learning with the interaction of traditional, face-to-face learning. Blended learning is an instructional strategy that converts the curriculum into computerized topics and multimedia such as images and sounds to make the educational process more effective and valuable (Aladejana, 2009; Yapici & Akbayin, 2012).

The uniqueness of the blended learning is represented by its ability to use the refined techniques from both, e-learning and traditional method; thus, the output will be a version of the best from each method. According to Kuo, Belland, Schroder, and Walker (2014), blended learning is an approach that combines face-to-face interactions with technology-based learning. Blended

learning can also be regarded as hybrid learning, and it is based upon face-to-face interactions 67% of the time and technology interactions 33% of the time. While the idea is to have the technology portion less than 50% of the time, teachers want to use the technology-based pieces as a way to enhance their instruction.

Blended learning is a thriving approach to integrating technology, including mobile technologies, into standard classrooms (Moskal, Dziuban, & Hartman, 2013). Blended learning can provide a more personalized and learner-centred learning experience while still allowing the learner to readily access instructor support. The importance of using the internet and computers is gradually increasing in terms of passing out instruction. Activities carried out during the usual teaching hour are not sufficiently effective because of time constraints; hence, with the blended learning model, learners are able to carry out multimedia applications – which cannot be sufficiently taught during lessons - via the internet. In view of the above, the interest of the researcher is to examine the effect of blended instructional strategy on the learning outcome of adults undertaking professional accounting programmes in Southwest, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of blended instructional strategy on the learning outcome of adults undertaking professional accounting programmes in Southwest, Nigeria

Specifically, the study examined:

- the homogeneity of the experimental and control groups before treatment; and
- the learning outcome of the experimental and control groups after treatment;

Research Questions

What are the effects of blended learning and conventional strategies on the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme?

What are the effects of blended learning and conventional strategies on the attitude of adults undertaking professional accounting programme towards learning?

Hypotheses

Based on the aforementioned questions the following hypotheses were generated:

- 1) There is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment
- 2) There is no significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking professional accounting programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment
- 3) There is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment
- 4) There is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before and after treatment.
- 5) There is no significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking professional accounting programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment

Research Design

This study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test two group designs (one experimental group and one control group). The baseline of the knowledge of adults undertaking professional accounting programme that was used for the study and homogeneity was established by pre-test while post-test was used after the treatment to measure learning outcome. The pattern of the design is as shown below.

Experimental group (E) $O_1 X_1 O_2$

Control group (C) $O_3 X_c O_4$

Where:

O_1, O_3 – (Observations before treatment)

O₂, O₄ – (Observations after treatment)

X₁ – Treatment (Blended learning Strategy)

X_c – Treatment (Conventional method)

Population

The population targeted for the study consisted of all adults undertaking professional accounting programme in 9 centres in Southwest, Nigeria.

Sample and sampling techniques

The sample consisted of 41 adults undertaking accounting professional programme (intact class size), drawn from two study centres in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample was selected using a multistage sampling procedure.

In stage one, two states were selected from Southwest, Nigeria, using a simple random sampling technique. The next stage involved the selection of a study centre from each of the two states through a purposive sampling technique. In stage three, the intact size of each of the two study centres were used for the study.

Research Instruments

Two instruments were used for collecting the data of the study. The instruments are Performance Test in Basic Accounting (PTBA) and Attitudinal Learning Scale (ALS). PTBA was used to measure the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme. It consisted of two sections, Sections A and B. Section A sought the bio-data of the respondents, while section B consisted of 30 objectives items with four options. The items covered all the topics to be taught for six weeks. The PTBA was used for both pre-test and post-test for data collection. The pre-test was designed to test the homogeneity of the two groups.

ALS also consisted of two sections, Sections A and B. Section A sought for bio-data of the respondents, while section B consisted of 20 items that sought for the attitude of adults undertaking professional accounting programmes towards learning.

Validity and reliability of the instruments

The instruments were validated by face, content, and criterion relative (concurrent) validity methods. It was given to three seasoned instructors of ICAN learning centres. The central exam conducted by ICAN was used as a criterion test to validate PTBA, and the validity coefficient obtained was 0.83. Cronbach Alpha formula was used to establish the reliability coefficient of 0.81 for PTBA and 0.76 for ALS

Experimental Procedure

The study was carried out in three phases:

Phase I: Pre-treatment stage (1 week)

To carry out the research in the centers, the researcher obtained permission from the authorities of the learning centres. A day workshop on the use and application of blended learning instructional strategy was organized for the research assistants that handled the experimental group. The researcher administered the pre-test and attitudinal scale instruments on both experimental and control groups in order to ascertain the homogeneity of the two groups.

Phase II: Treatment stage (6 weeks)

Blended Learning: Adults undertaking professional accounting programme are exposed to two sessions of learning per week for six consecutive weeks. They were involved in twelve sessions consecutively, covering a module using the blended learning instructional strategy.

Control Group: Control group has no special treatment. They are taught via conventional method (normal classroom interaction) for six weeks.

Phase III: Post-treatment Stage

At the end of the treatment stage, PTBA and ALS were re-administered on the adults undertaking accounting professional programme to determine the effects of the treatment on them. The options of the same PTBA used during the pre-test were re-arranged to avoid test-wiseness and administered to the experimental and control groups.

Data Analysis

The data collected through the instruments were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using means, standard deviation, and bar chart. Hypotheses 1 – 3 and 5, were tested using a t-test, while hypothesis 4 was tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Descriptive Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the effects of blended learning and conventional strategies on the performance of adults undertaking accounting professional programme?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of performance before and after treatment

Strategies	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Blended Learning	Before Treatment	17	34.82	0.81	31.24
	After Treatment	17	66.06	7.08	
Conventional	Before Treatment	24	34.54	1.10	21.75
	After Treatment	24	56.29	3.29	
Total		41			

From Table 1, it is shown that the mean difference in performance before and after treatment for blended learning instructional strategy is 31.24, and the conventional method is 21.75. It appears that the use of Blended Learning and Conventional strategies influences the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme with blended learning strategies being the more effective strategy of instruction. The graphical representation below further shows the more effective strategy of instruction.

Fig -1: Performance before and after treatment of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended learning and Conventional strategies

Research Question 2: What are the effects of blended learning and conventional strategies on the attitude of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards learning before and after treatment

Strategies	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Blended Learning	Before Treatment	17	44.82	0.73	21.77
	After Treatment	17	66.59	2.53	
Conventional	Before Treatment	24	44.83	1.00	13.69
	After Treatment	24	58.52	2.67	
Total		41			

From Table 2, it is shown that the mean difference in attitude towards learning before and after treatment for blended learning instructional strategy is 21.77 and the conventional method is 13.69. It appears that the use of Blended Learning and Conventional strategies influences the attitude of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning with blended learning

strategy being the more effective strategy. The graphical representation below further shows the more effective strategy influencing attitude towards learning.

Fig-2: Attitude before and after treatment of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning exposed to Blended learning and Conventional strategies

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment

Table 3: t-test analysis for the difference in the performance of adults exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Blended Learning	17	34.82	0.81	39	0.896	0.376
Conventional	24	34.54	1.10			

P>0.05

Table 3 shows that the t-cal value of 0.896 is not significant because the P-value (0.376) > 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment. This implies that the groups were homogeneous at the commencement of the study.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment.

Table 4: t-test analysis for the difference in the attitude of adults towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Blended Learning	17	44.82	0.73	39	0.034	0.973
Conventional	24	44.83	1.01			

P > 0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 0.034 is not significant because the P-value (0.973) > 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before treatment.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment.

Table 5: t-test analysis for the difference in the performance of adults exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Blended Learning	17	66.06	7.08	39	5.938*	0.000
Conventional	24	56.29	3.29			

*P < 0.05

Table 5 shows that the t-cal value of 5.938 is significant because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment. The mean score showed a significant mean difference of 9.77 in favour of Blended learning instructional strategy.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before and after treatment.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for performance before and after treatment

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1082.780 ^a	2	541.390	22.449*	.000
Intercept	505.253	1	505.253	20.950*	.000
Before Treatment	33.460	1	33.460	1.387	.224
Group	1032.923	1	1032.923	42.830*	.000
Error	916.439	38	24.117		
Total	151184.000	41			
Corrected Total	1899.220	40			

a. R Squared = .542 (Adjusted R Squared = .517) * P < 0.05

The result presented in Table 6 shows that there is a significant difference in the performance of adults in the groups (blended learning and control groups) as P= 0.000<0.05. This result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. By implication, there is a significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before and after treatment. In order to find out the more probable effective strategy, Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) was carried out. The result is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) of performance by treatment

Grand Mean = 61.18

Variable + Category	N	Unadjusted Dev'n	Eta ²	Adjusted for Independent + Covariate	Beta
Experimental (Blended Learning)	17	4.88	.81	4.79	.19
Control	24	-4.89		-4.93	
Multiple R					.736
Multiple R ²					.542

The result in Table 7 shows the Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) of performance by treatment. It reveals that, with a grand mean of 61.18, the group exposed to blended learning had a higher adjusted mean score of 66.06 (61.18+4.88) than their counterparts in the control group 56.29(61.18+(-4.89)). This means that a blended learning instructional strategy was the more effective strategy of instruction in ICAN learning centres. The treatment explained about 84% (Eta² = 0.81) of the observed variance in performance. The two treatment strategies accounted for 54.2% (R² = 0.542) contribution to the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment.

Table 8: t-test analysis for the difference in the attitude of adults towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Blended Learning	17	66.59	2.53	39	9.871*	0.000
Conventional	24	58.42	2.67			

*P<0.05

Table 8 shows that the t-cal value of 9.871 is significant because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking accounting professional programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment. The mean score showed a significant mean difference of 8.17 in favour of Blended learning instructional strategy.

Discussion

The finding of this study revealed that the performance and attitude before treatment of adults undertaking professional accounting programme in both experimental and control groups are low and do not differ statistically. This finding established the homogeneity of the two groups involved in the study prior to the experiment. In other words, it could be said that the knowledge baseline for the two groups involved in the study are equal. Consequently, any significant difference recorded after treatment would not be ascribed to chance, but to the specific treatment applied.

The findings of this study revealed that there was a significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment. Likewise, there was a significant difference in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies before and after treatment. Both findings showed that blended learning instructional strategy was the more effective strategy of instruction in ICAN learning centres.

There was a better improvement in the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme resulting from their exposure to the Blended Learning strategy. This implies that the introduction of Blended Learning to the experimental group made them perform better than the control group that was not exposed to the treatment. This study agrees with the findings of Aladejana (2009), Yapici and Akbayin (2012), and Chandra and Watters (2012) that Blended learning strategy application yielded better results than the conventional method because it gives flexibility for students' learning in terms of learning style and study time, it improves students' experience and enhances their engagement.

The findings of this study revealed a significant difference in the attitude of adults undertaking professional accounting programme towards learning exposed to Blended Learning and Conventional strategies after treatment. The reason for this finding might be because Blended Learning integrates face to face and technology interaction, which facilitates proper assimilation and comprehension. This study is in conformity with the findings of Yapici and Akbayin (2012)

that the use of appropriate instructional techniques during the teaching-learning process enhances students' attitudes towards learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that the two groups (Blended learning and Conventional) were homogeneous at the commencement of the experiment. The use of Blended Learning and Conventional strategy enhanced the performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme while Blended Learning is the more effective. The attitude of adults undertaking professional accounting programme was enhanced when exposed to the Blended learning strategy.

Recommendations

Based on the following findings, it is hereby recommended that:

The use of a Blended Learning strategy should be encouraged in professional accounting programme learning centres so as to enhance better performance of adults undertaking professional accounting programme.

Instructors in professional accounting programme learning centres should be given adequate orientation through workshops and seminars to update their knowledge in the use of Blended Learning strategy in teaching.

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I am Olanipekun O.A. of the Department of Adult Education and Community Development, Ekiti State University. I am currently an Assistant Lecturer.

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